

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LEARNERS INVOLVEMENT IN LEARNER'S DISCIPLINE MANAGEMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA

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Abstract:

The research aimed to analyze critically the effectiveness of the learners' involvement in the learner's discipline management in primary schools in Kenya. The objectives below guided in the study development; To critically analyze the extent to which learners' involvement in the formulation of the school rules and regulations influence management of the learners discipline in schools; To critically analyze the extent to which learner's assistance in time management affect discipline management in schools in Kenya. To critically analyze the extent to which learners democratic rights to elect the children's government body influence learner's discipline management in schools; To critically analyze the learners observation of hygiene and sanitation help in discipline management in primary schools; To critically analyze to what extent do learner's involvement in planning co-curricular activities assist in learner's discipline management in primary schools. The study used qualitative research method that guided in acquiring reliable and valid information on the study. The study recommends to the government through the ministry of Education coming up with proper policies and guidelines to ensure effective involvement and engagement of learners in discipline management in primary schools.

Keywords: discipline, indiscipline, management, learners, involvement

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1. Introduction

Learners discipline management, plays a very important role in the smooth running of learning institutions in the world. The problem of discipline management globally has been an issue of concern stakeholders. Discipline is the backbone of the national unity where the disciplined and united citizens are able to work more smoothly and this can be reflected to the learners' spirit of unity, co-operation and brotherhood in the leaning institutions. The learners remain key custodian of any learning institution, without learners there could be no school. Every school has a unique set of rule and regulation which guides the learner's conduct within the school premises.

The school management has a responsibility to ensure that all learners abide to the rules and regulations of their school. Therefore, learners discipline cannot be separated from the other components of instructional programs in the school, those who fail to follow the set rules, and regulations are disciplined accordingly. Indiscipline amongst the learners in primary schools is commonly caused by the external social environment, Drugs and drug abuse, poor parenting to nurture the children's discipline. Chanda, Songolo and Mutekenya (2015),citing short(1988), argued that promoting learners self-esteem and belongingness has more positive effect in reducing behavioral problems than punishing wrong doers in primary schools.

The pupils approaches in discipline management, seeks to promote peer counseling, Learners awareness of the school rules and regulations, promoting clubs and societies in school, engaging with learners in co-curricular activity planning, involving learners in decision making like formulation of school rules and regulations. Corporal punishment to learners was abolished and laid great emphasis on solving learners' problems through guidance and counseling, training learners in making reasonable and independence decisions in managing the learners discipline in primary schools in Kenya.

The learners should be given well advised and freed to express their problems to the school administration or their instructors through the set channels. While the administration should also use the same channels to sensitize the learners on the best discipline expected from them while in school compound. The findings may be useful to the school administration, Ministry of Education and other Education stakeholders to come up with possible solutions which may involve learners in managing discipline in primary schools in Kenya.

2. Statement of the Problem

The bringing up of disciplined learners in primary schools is unavoidable in all the countries with keen focus to achieve a disciplined citizens in future who are determined and active who may reflect in the Kenyan's vision 2030. Apart from the government establishing the 8.4.4 education system in Kenya through the Ministry of Education (M.O.E) the government has further offered free Education for all learners in primary level since 2003. This attracted millions of children to enroll for schooling, including of the late Kimani Maruge, who is the holder of Guinness World Record for the oldest person to start primary school in 2004 at 84 years old. Learners have enjoyed this free offer but it came with a lot of challenges to many schools. Among the problems reported are indiscipline cases like Drugs abuse and drugs trafficking, absenteeism, late coming, being unruly, not doing class work assignments, use vernacular languages as a medium of communication within school compound. These vices lured pupils into indiscipline cases like associating with school drop-outs, prostitution and drug peddlers which interfere with their standard of living in Kenyan schools. It is in this co-relation that led to involving learners in discipline management in schools that saw the need to carry out this research. Learners in the past have been treated like objects and not to be heard but only to be pumped with knowledge and skills. Whenever things go wrong they were the center of blame and never given space to express their minds and participate in schools decision making which has led for this study to manage indiscipline cases in many Kenyan schools in the primary sector.

3. Purpose of the Study

Aim of the research was to critically analyze the effectiveness of the learners' involvement in the learners discipline management in the primary schools.

4. The Objectives of the Study

The research was based on stated objectives below:

1. To critically analyze how learners involvement in the formulation of the school rules and regulations influence learners discipline management in Kenyan primary schools.
2. To critically analyze the extent to which learners assistance to time management affects learners discipline management in primary schools.

3. To critically analyze the extent to which learners democratic rights to elect the children's government body influence discipline management in Kenyan primary schools.
4. To critically analyze how learners observation to hygiene and sanitation help influence discipline management in Kenyan primary schools.
5. To critically analyze to which extent do involvement of learners planning in co-curricular activities assist in learners discipline management in Kenyan primary schools.

5. Research Questions

Research questions for the study were:

1. How is the learner's involvement in formulation of school rules and regulations influence learner's discipline management in Kenyan primary schools?
2. How do learner's assistance in time management affect discipline management in Kenyan primary schools?
3. What challenges do learners face when exercising their democratic rights of electing the children's government body in Kenyan primary schools?
4. How do learner's observation to hygiene and sanitation affect the discipline management in Kenyan primary schools?
5. How has learners' involvement in planning of co-curricular activities influence discipline management in Kenyan primary schools?

6. Significance of the Study

The research findings pointed out fundamental tools that could be of great use to the government through the Ministry Of Education and other stakeholders in Education field to formulate policies based on involving learners in formulation of school rules and regulations to manage discipline among learners in schools. The finding would be beneficial to parents and school administration to bring up discipline and law abiding pupils in and outside the school compound. The study may help in development of learner's self-discipline and responsible as they observe time management while in school by following the school time table which is emphasized through organizing guidance and counseling from the teachers. The study would be important to learners to learners as they are enlightened by the policies from the government through the Education Ministry on their democratic rights to elect their leaders of their choice in the school children's government body. The study would be beneficial to the government

through the Ministry Of Education, Health and Sanitation through the learners responsibility of observing and keeping environment free from out-break of health related diseases and promoting good academic atmosphere in the school compound. The study benefited learners through participation of co-curricular activities as not all learners are gifted academically. Those gifted in games and sports would nurture the skill which maintains their body physically fit and may get job from sports and games companies in future and earn their living.

7. Research Methodology

The study was a critical analysis on effectiveness of the learners' involvement in learners discipline management in primary schools in Kenya. The study used qualitative research method that guided in acquiring reliable and valid information which led to promoting socialness in learning activities, according to Bandura theory. The research used content and desk design in the analysis which allowed for the critique of the literature on the effectiveness of learners involvement in discipline management in primary schools in Kenya.

8. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework was based on the behavioral learning theory as put forward by Bandura. (1977), who advocated that behavior of man is learnt and acquired mostly through seeing and imitation. Today children are surrounded by a lot of environmental influence like teachers, parents, Television and peer groups. When they tent to portray good behavior, the children will try to imitate the good treads from them, but if majority in the society are characterized by indiscipline behaviors, learners will definitely imitate some of these behaviors from their homes and schools thus becoming hard to manage discipline among learners in schools.

When learners observe good and discipline people in the society being rewarded for exemplary behavior they will tent to imitate such behaviors so that they can be recognized and rewarded in school. Junior learners in the school will tent to imitate majority of their senior learners. If they behave well in the school, the junior learners will do imitate the good discipline from them so that they may be seen as good children. This implies that the people around the children contribute a lot in their behavior in and outside school community. A child who is rewarded in school for being good and disciplined may likely continue with that good behavior while in school and in future outside the world. The learners are also more likely to imitate behaviors of

adults and this may show the behaviors that may come from learners. Learners can also learn from the streets and public places that violence is a means of solving a problem an experienced from workers who often go on strike demanding their welfare fulfillments like salary hike and later they get their demands this may lead learners imitate violence and strikes against their teachers and administration as they demand their rights.

9. Critique Literature Review

9.1 A critical Analysis on Learners Involvement in Learner's Discipline Management

Discipline in any society of parents, learners, and educator is of paramount concern. It is the expectations of the parents and educators in the entire society to bring up their children in a responsible behavior within and without school community. The acceptable behavior among learners will help produce disciplined and law abiding citizens in future. To achieve these moral values among the learners an effective involvement of learners and all other stakeholders as per Ministry Of Education (2001) documentation in managing learners discipline in primary schools being important as children need to be involved in decision making in the schools especially the activities which affect them directly.

The involvement in decision making among the learners could be direct where they meet face to face with their instructors or indirect through elected children's governing body. Among the activities to involve learners in promoting discipline within the school includes; peer counseling, guidance and counseling. All these may help learners interact among themselves and experts in the field of guidance and counseling to an open discussion and guide them accordingly to grow morally upright. This creates peace and harmony in the school community between learners and administration. This involvement of learners in school decision making may instill discipline management in primary schools in Kenya.

9.2 A Critical Analysis on Learners Discipline Management in Primary Schools

Discipline is a main requirement in any civilized set up of life in the world .Majority of primary schools in the world, Kenya included cases of indiscipline have grown rapidly not only in the learning institutions but also in religious activities, political and family activities where discipline is necessary. The act of indiscipline has caused a lot of concern in the country among the administrators, educators, education stakeholders and parents as per (Wayson and Pinnell, 1994). Indiscipline cases have grown perhaps because many of the school going children come from indiscipline society, poverty affected areas, single-parents which affect moral upbringing of children (Kute, 2014). A

poor supervision of learners by parents and teachers lead to a negative regards towards all set of authorities in schools and communities.

School is a recognized agent of socialization where discipline among learners is promoted. Two main approaches are used in schools to instill discipline among learners; that is formal and informal approaches. Formal as the main approach to promote discipline includes; classroom setup, guidance and counseling, school clubs and societies all help learners acquire some social life skills and duties which are vital to the pupil's discipline growth. The informal approach include peer groups influence and guidance and counseling from parents and school Board of Management (BOM). School curriculum designed to equip learners with basic knowledge, skills, attitudes and other opportunities to achieve different social and vocational talents hence playing fundamental role to build valuable members in the school community with good values and attitudes acceptable to the societal norms.

According to Griffins (1994), the main importance aim of discipline in school is to ensure every child has good behaviors and conduct themselves morally either under supervision, controlled or else forced as these are the demands of any community on its members for happiness and productivity. The discipline of the learners in any society is a comprehensive involvement of all parties. Deviance from discipline amounts to poor performance (Williams, 1982) and M.O.E, 2001). Indiscipline owes its origin in the learner's minds as documented by Okumbe (2001) sources indicates that school children have turned violent to their instructors and colleagues due to indiscipline according to (Thinguri & Kiongo,(2015). All schools have a duty to deal with learners vices like drug and substance abuse, drug trafficking, sexual assault, rape, stealing, sneaking from schools, absenteeism, lateness among other indiscipline behavior as per (M.O.E.1991, Kiongo & Thinguri, 2015).

9.3 A critical Analysis on How Learners Involvement in Formulation of School Rules and Regulations Influence Learners Discipline Management

A well-organized society is built in a well set of moral laws to be followed by its members. This definite set of moral laws governs and controls the behavior of those living in that society. School learners need to adhere to the school rules and regulations. The school should have a well formulated rules and regulations which guides to the smooth running of the school programs. These rules and regulations need to be acceptable in the school community, nationally and internationally. During the rules and regulation formulation, the following stakeholders need to be fully consulted and involved; school administration, government through the Ministry Of Education, educators and learners. The set rules may be posted on the school open places like;

school notice boards, classrooms and learners given copies of the same on which they must adhere to them once in school. The learners may fill owning the rules and the regulations they were consulted, involved and contributed during the formulation enhancing easy acceptance and adhering to them (Kimweli, 2013). This may help maintain learners discipline in schools as each rule has to handle a case as per its strength and weight it deserves. Among the rules formed may deal with school uniform, misuse of school resources, absenteeism, fighting in school, stealing, lateness in school, cleanliness, medial of communication while in schools, when and where to take food while in school compound.

9.4 A Critical Analysis on the Extent to which Learners Assistance in Time Management Affects Learners Discipline Management

Management of time is one of the people's major challenges in life. In smooth running of every organization and institution there is need for time keeping to determine how long an activity should take to be accomplished. It's noted that, an effective time keeping among learners in schools starts with proper organization, planning and establishing rules and regulations that makes learners avoid time wastage in schools. Time management and punctuality problems tend to have negative impact on discipline matters of the learners (Sultan, 2013) Time spend out of class internationally accounts to less than 25 percent of the total time a learner spends in school per day, Such time spend out of class includes; break time, lunchtime and games time are important to learners relaxation after class work. The need for learners to balance their time in school is of importance as it goes hand in hand with learner's discipline in managing their activities as per the time allocated in the school time table.

9.5 A Critical Analysis on the Extent to Which Learners Democratic Right to Elect the Children Government Body Influence Learners Discipline Management in Primary Schools

Learner education has greatly been assumed for too long as an important role in promoting room for democracy not only in the society but also in the schools. According to Carr & Hartnett, (1996), it is necessary in education sector to promote democratic space more on individual and especially the learners in school set up of management and leadership is an important step in any planned reforms in schools which controls and manages devolved skills like leadership and responsibility from a central point of school administration to learners elected children's body leaders according to (UNESCO, 2005). In a wide democratic space where teachers, parents and administration have to take a school-based decision and promote democratic skills and

spirit to observe certain level of decentralizing school autonomy although the autonomy may not mean a totality guarantee on decision making in school.

This makes learners play an important role in attaining more democratic skills, like leadership in their children's body. Policy implementation like making decisions may be constituted by major stakeholders in the schools. According to Bean & Apple, (1999) evidenced that, strong attention from learners promotes their involvement through entrusting them powers and duties which in the long run this will encourage and promote learners in Kenya through their own elected children's body leaders make choice who shall effectively control command and direct the pupils welfare in discipline management primary institutions.

9.6 A Critical Analysis on How Learners Observation to Hygiene and Sanitation Influences Learners Discipline Management in Primary Schools

The Introduction of Free Primary Education (F.P.E), 2003) in Kenya has brought a positive and a negative impact in learning institutions. The enrolment in schools has doubled, leading to shortage of school learning facilities and resources like; few classrooms and hostels to accommodate high population in the schools, shortage of books and learning resources. Majority of the learner's parents from rural area are of low earning and have poor living standards which affect either gender of boys or girls welfare in school. A good number of girls in schools may ran away from schools to avoid embarrassment especially during their menstrual periods due lack of sanitary pads as the government supply of the same is not enough for the large enrolments.

Poor living environment and compounds is a reflection of irresponsible learners and may lead to outbreak of diseases like malaria, cholera among other diseases related to untidy environment. The Kenyan government through the Ministry Of Education should come up with policies ideally to retain learners in school by allocating adequate funds to develop sanitation resources like timely provision of sanitary towels to girls, training learners on hygiene and sanitation in the school environment. The help to control truancy gives learners self-confidence and responsibility as learners can make decisions on their own. As per (Osters,2010) hygiene and sanitation is vital in retention of learners in school thus management of discipline among learners in primary schools is promoted as the learners may not be highly affected by outside school environment and interaction with indiscipline school drop-outs.

9.7 A Critical Analysis on The Extent to Which Learners Involvement in Planning Co-Curricular Activities Assist in Learners Discipline Management in Kenyan Primary Schools

A part from academic excellence which is one of the main goals for learners in schools, co-curriculum activities are also import for pupil's physical development. Learners also need to be given opportunity to nurture their talents outside classroom. This is because not all children going to school are academically talented. Some learners will do well academically while others will perform well in co-curricular activities and earn their future from those talent activities like football, athletics, gymnastics and acrobatics among others. There are other skills acquired by learners outside classroom such as developing interpersonal relationships, working together, respecting one another, cultural, physical, societal and spiritual way of putting learners together in the field.

The above learned skills are very important to learner's individual success in life as it contributes to their future life outside school. Activities outside classroom makes learners happier and more active especially when they are freed to express their skills and learn other skills like time management as each game is allocated a specific time, this helps them acquire the time management skill, self-discipline as they have to follow the rules set for each game, develop self-confidence, create team work, tolerance and co-operation and respect to one another. The co-curricular activities need involvement of learners in organizing, planning and selection of the team players. Participation of learners needs to be done freely without forces from administration. During learners practice to follow the rules of different games they may also reflect the same in school compound thus learners discipline is managed in primary schools in Kenya.

10. Conclusion

The main aim of carrying out this research is to critically analyze the effectiveness of the learner's involvement in discipline management in primary schools in Kenya. It was established that cases of indiscipline in primary school leaners has grown too high not only in Kenya but also globally. The research also found that lack of learner's involvement in school decision making like formulation of school rules and regulation affect learner's discipline. The common components of these indiscipline cases in schools include; stealing, truancy, fighting, noisemaking, drug abuse and bullying. The school educators and learners have believes that indiscipline among learners can be instilled through learners guidance and counseling, involvement school parents, give close supervision of learners duties, assignments and encourage peer counseling, punishment to be administered to rude learners. It is worthy effective to use

communication skills to encourage learners to express their views and problems through the proper set channels to the administration rather than burning schools, boycotting classes and not doing class work assignments as a way of expressing their aguish while in school.

11. Recommendations

The study recommended the following key actions

1. Learners discipline treads and its effective management in primary schools to be promoted in the school community through the collaboration of the parents and school administration to help produce disciplined and a law abiding citizens in future.
2. The government through the Ministry Of Education to formulate guideline policies which involve learners in formulation of school rules and regulations in schools to enhance effective awareness and abiding of school rules and regulations.
3. Education stakeholders should ensure learners observe time management by giving moral values through guidance and counseling sessions done by their instructors which promote productivity in academic results, seriousness in their duties and avoid time wastage.
4. The Ministry Of Education through the school administration, learners need to be enlightened on the importance of children's government body to their welfare in school and their democratic rights to elect leaders of their choice in the children government council.
5. The school administration in collaboration with the children's government body to ensure good learning atmosphere and a clean environment to promote learning among the learners and control outbreak of diseases which may affect smooth learning of the learners.
6. School administration need to involve learners in planning and participating in co-curricular activities in schools to promote their talent, social skills, discipline management and co-operation among the participating learners

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